

Abschlussbericht: Digitizing Corbridge Roman Town

Researcher: Prof. Dr. Catherine Teitz

Institution: Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz

Funding Period: 15 May – 15 November, 2025

Funding Institution: BMFTR-Datenkompetenzzentrum HERMES

Introduction

The project “Digitizing Corbridge Roman Town” has been transformed with the support of the HERMES-Forschungsstudienprogramm für Datenkompetenzen in den Geistes- und Kulturwissenschaften at the Leibniz-Institut für Europäische Geschichte. The aim of the project was to produce the first geographic information system for the Roman site at Corbridge, mapping both the structures visible today and those known only from excavation. This funding made it possible to conduct a comprehensive survey and documentation campaign, building a foundation upon which the legacy data could be integrated into a new system.

More than a century of research has produced a huge quantity of inconsistent, analogue spatial information. The variation in everything from basic location names to numerical systems has made it difficult to integrate datasets and to study the site. The key objectives of this project were (1) to synthesize and standardize the existing information, (2) to enhance it with new documentation of the architecture, and (3) to integrate the data into a single GIS, made freely available to enable new research. The HERMES funding supported an extensive architectural survey campaign at Corbridge and the subsequent data processing between May and November 2025. The project was conducted in collaboration with English Heritage, which manages the site, and with support from Historic England. The geospatial data produced as part of this project is being published open-access with the Archaeological Data Service in its Data Catalogue. This report reviews the work undertaken for each of the project objectives and discusses the larger outcomes.

I. Synthesize and Standardize Existing Information

Before any new system could be implemented to identify – by name or spatially – the structures at Corbridge, it was necessary to evaluate and synthesize the existing spatial information. From this basis, it was possible to develop a standardized system for the new survey and GIS that reflected the historic practices at the site while following a consistent and usable structure. To identify the structures at Corbridge, it was necessary to build a “Site ID” database that integrated all historic excavations, referred to spatial features in a consistent format, and provided a standardized location reference system that could be used in GIS, in discussions of the site, and in the English Heritage Historic Object Management System (HOMS) database, which records all of the finds in the Corbridge museum. Due to the excavation and documentation protocols at Corbridge, it has been impossible to search for objects by location on site in HOMS.

While many buildings at Corbridge have been referred to by a site number since excavation began in 1906, the “Cor Site ID” was conceived as a way to consistently refer to structures (broadly defined) and to describe their spatial and/or architectural features with increasing specificity. Each unique Cor Site ID could refer to an entire building, an area or room within a structure, a road, open space, or excavation trenches or areas. Cor Site IDs use decimal points to increase specificity within a structure; the first number before the decimal is either the ‘site number’ as the structure was defined during excavation or a new number (beginning with 100) assigned to something not numbered during excavation. After the first decimal point, a second

number indicates larger areas, and subsequent decimal points mark increasingly smaller ones (eg. working from the entire structure to a specific quadrant within in a room could be A.B.C.D with A as the site number for the structure, B as one defined section of the structure, C as a room, and D as a quadrant within the room).

To gather all of the structures, open spaces, and excavation areas known from Corbridge required a thorough evaluation of the sources. Excavation reports and published plans for the excavations from 1906-1914 and 1947-1980 describe the structures found and their component parts, but without any consistency; there is variation between Arabic and Roman numerals, Latin and English names, and some structures or rooms are renumbered between excavation seasons. All of this information was gathered in a preliminary table to create a concordance between the Roman numerals, Arabic numerals, site name, Latin name, English descriptive name, and alternative names. In addition to what was known from reports, the mid-twentieth century excavations employed a ‘Four Figure Code’ system, in which a number-letter combination identified a particular area of work on site. These codes could include both spatial (from general area to structure or trench) and stratigraphic information in wildly varied formats. There are 7,284 codes recorded in the excavation Finds Notebooks. Each code was reviewed, its location in space determined, and a Site ID was assigned or newly created as necessary.

The Site ID database was created as a table (Fig. 1) without geospatial information, to serve as the foundation for the GIS. The fields of the database include:

- Cor_Site_ID_Num: the Site ID as numbers only
- Cor_Site_ID: the Site ID with the prefix “COR.” (prefix required for integration with English Heritage HOMS)
- Cor_Site_ID_short: shortens the Site ID to one or two decimals, creating larger spatial groups
- Site_Name: a descriptive name for each Site ID, including the site number where possible and/or the type of structure; alternatively, the name given to the excavation area/trench
- Structure_Type: uses the English Heritage standardized vocabulary to describe its type of structure/feature (17 options)
- Visibility: uses set terms to describe its visibility within the 2025 guardianship area of Corbridge Roman Fort and Town (excavation – an excavation trench or area; planned – a structure known from a site plan but no longer visible; visible – currently visible on site)
- Ex_Years: the years in which excavation took place (as determined from site reports and Four Figure Codes)

Figure 1: A section of the Site ID database

Cor_Site_ID_Num	Cor_Site_ID	Cor_Site_ID_short	Site_Name	Structure_Type	Visibility	Ex_Years
4.8.1	COR.4.8.1	COR.4.8	Site 4W, north end	excavation area	excavation	1961
4.8.2	COR.4.8.2	COR.4.8	Site 4W, south end	excavation area	excavation	1961
4.9	COR.4.9	COR.4.9	Site 4 Strip Building	strip building		1907, 1913
6.1	COR.6.1	COR.6.1	Gate to the Compounds	gate	visible	1907, 1936
7.1	COR.7.1	COR.7.1	East Granary, Site 7	storage structure	visible	1907, 1908, 1909, 1913, 1937, 1946, 1947, 1948
7.2	COR.7.2	COR.7.1	North of East Granary	excavation area	excavation	1949, 1950, 1951
7.3	COR.7.3	COR.7.1	Late wall SE corner	feature	excavation	1907
8.1	COR.8.1	COR.8.1	Fountain, Site 8	water	visible	1907, 1908, 1946, 1949
8.2	COR.8.2	COR.8.1	South of Fountain	excavation area	excavation	1948
9.1	COR.9.1	COR.9.1	Site 9, Strip Building	strip building	excavation	1908, 1980
10.1	COR.10.1	COR.10.1	West Granary, Site 10	storage structure	visible	1908, 1909, 1934, 1946, 1948, 1960, 1962
10.2	COR.10.2	COR.10.1	North of West Granary	excavation area	excavation	1948, 1950

II. New Architectural Documentation

The funding from HERMES for this project supported the architectural documentation of Corbridge and the subsequent integration of the data into the site's GIS. In order to assign the Site IDs accurate and meaningful spatial information, it was essential to undertake the first drone and GPS-enabled surveys of the structures visible and consolidated within the English Heritage-managed site, known as the Guardianship area. These surveys would make it possible to draw the Site IDs accurately within a GIS shapefile and to georeference the historic plans and drawings. The architectural documentation used two different instruments: a drone and a total station.

The first phase was a drone flight over the site, undertaken by the Geospatial Survey Team at Historic England and facilitated by the cooperation agreement between English Heritage and Historic England. On 25 June, 2025 in ideal cloudy conditions, Historic England arrived (before the site opened to the public) to fly two different drones over the area. The drones captured high resolution images, which produced a detailed orthophoto (Fig. 2), suitable for georeferencing plans, as well as a 3D model of the structures. To allow the images and model to be integrated spatially, Historic England set temporary benchmarks on the site, which remained in place through the subsequent total station survey.

Figure 2: The orthophoto of Corbridge (Historic England)

The second and more substantial phase of architectural documentation was a total station survey of the standing structures in the guardianship area. The work was conducted by Alex Turner of SAT Archaeology using a remote total station, allowing him to work alone. The survey required 14 days of fieldwork conducted between 28 July and 19 August, 2025. Over the course of the work, Turner took more than 25,000 points to document every corner, angle, and change in level (from foundation to upper courses) for every visible structure (Fig. 3). The results of this survey were individual GPS points, which represented changes in the architectural features. To become usable data, the points had to be connected into outlines (polygons in a shapefile) to represent the structures. Using the orthophoto from Historic England as a reference, Turner traced the foundations and upper courses of the structures into distinct and labeled polygons (Fig. 4); the Z-axis information from the survey is preserved but flattened while working in two-dimensions.

Figure 3: The architectural survey points as taken over 14 days of fieldwork by A. Turner

Figure 4: The survey points converted into polygons indicating the foundations and upper courses of the structures

III. Integration into a new GIS

Once the surveys and initial processing of the data was complete, the next stage of the project was the integration of the legacy and modern data together into a site GIS. The Site ID database provided a consistent reference system and, following this structure, it was possible to draw a new plan of Corbridge as a polygon shapefile that represented all locations in the database.

The two new architectural surveys were the geospatially correct foundation for this work. The orthophoto and the polygon plan of the structures accurately represented the site's architecture, providing an anchor for georeferencing the historic archaeological plans. Relatively very little of the Roman settlement is now visible in English Heritage guardianship area; a much larger extent was excavated in the early twentieth century. These excavations were documented with extensive plans and sections by the trained architect W. Knowles. The high level of accuracy in the plans has become clear through georeferencing the drawings to the visible structures, allowing for greater confidence in their use as a resource for drawing structures no longer visible. It would have been difficult to georeference the plans that did not overlap with the Guardianship area and visible structures; here, the project was fortunate to have access to an unpublished geophysical survey of the surrounding landscape. The geophysics was also undertaken and processed by Turner, then at Newcastle University, as part of the Corbridge Roman Station and Environs Project (PI: Ian Haynes). The geophysics revealed many of the structures known from excavation and enabled the accurate georeferencing of the plans. The georeferenced plans themselves are an important resource for research on the site, but they are also essential for drawing a new plan that represents all Site IDs. Using these pieces together – the orthophoto, the survey polygons, and historic plans – it was then possible to draw a Site ID plan for Corbridge. This plan represents not only the structures and their conventional subdivisions (wings of a building or rooms) but also the known or estimated extent of excavation trenches (Fig. 5). The visibility and structure type fields allow for better visualization of the data, separating between areas of archaeological work and Roman structures or spaces.

Figure 5: The Site ID plan for Corbridge (detail view)

Outcomes

The outcomes of this project include freely-accessible data and significant contributions to research on Roman Corbridge. The data generated as part of this project will be available on the Archaeological Data Service (ADS), a central and stable repository for archaeological work in the UK. The data will be published (under review as of February, 2026) as the collection “Mapping Corbridge Roman Town” within the new “Research on Corbridge Roman Fort and Town” hub on ADS. The collection acknowledges the key funding role of HERMES in the project. The collection includes both GIS and Data/CSV files. The GIS files are: the Site ID shapefile, Turner’s total station survey, Turner’s polygon and polyline shapefiles (created from the survey points), the Historic England orthophoto, and the georeferenced plans. The data files are the Site ID database as a CSV and a README file.

This project, the architectural surveys together with the development of the Site IDs, will enable new research in many different directions on Roman Corbridge. The site GIS is the first of its kind for Corbridge – previously all mapping had been analogue and without geospatial references. Its creation makes spatial analysis of structures (currently visible as well as only known from excavation reports) and objects possible at the site for any researcher with internet access to download the data. Through ongoing collaboration with English Heritage, the project also contributes to a better understanding of the archaeological collection at the site. The Site IDs are designed for integration with HOMS, using the Four Figure Codes (referenced in catalogue entries) as well as other site identifiers, to provide straightforward, consistent, and searchable spatial information for many objects in the collection. The hope of this project is that the spatial data and associated structure and location terminology serve as a consistent underlying foundation for future research on the site.

Project leader: Catherine Teitz ORCID - 0000-0002-0604-742X

Contributor: Alex Turner ORCID - 0000-0002-4305-1655